

Learning, transformative action, and grassroots innovation: Insights from the Spanish energy cooperative Som Energia.

Victoria Pellicer-Sifres^{a*}; Sergio Belda-Miquel^a; Ivan Cuesta-Fernandez^b; Alejandra Boni Aristizábal^a

^a INGENIO [CSIC-UPV], Universitat Politècnica de València, Camino de Vera s/n, Valencia, 46020, Spain.

Corresponding author (*): vicpelsi@ingenio.upv.es, 00 34 656 40 21 92

^b Centre of African Studies, University of Edinburgh, 15a George Square, Edinburgh, EH8 9LD, UK.

Word count: 8747 words without references, 9536 words including references

Highlights:

- On energy grassroots initiatives with transformative potential, first- (instrumental) and second-order (transformative) learning emerge.
- Micropolitical and macropolitical factors are drivers that influence the emergence of learning.
- Learning contributes to influence on macropolitical and micropolitical dynamics, through the promotion of different strategies towards sustainability.
- Radical transformative changes towards sustainability are achieved through an empowering process that transforms our current values and relations.

0. Abstract

“Grassroots innovations for sustainability are attracting increasing attention in academic, activist and policy debate. Although there is a recognition of their transformative potential, very little research has specifically been conducted on how transformative perspectives, strategies and actions emerge. This paper explores the role of learning in promoting transformative strategies towards sustainability. We develop a heuristic framework connecting ideas from social learning literature and Strategic Niche Management and address the case of Som Energia, the first renewable energy cooperative in Spain. Our results found that micropolitical and macropolitical factors are drivers that influence the emergence of first- and second-order learning. In turn, this learning moulds three different strategies proposed by this grassroots initiative, namely: commercial, social, and empowering strategies. Our results give insights to illustrate that, in order to develop radical transformative changes towards sustainability it is not enough to merely scale-up the regime (commercial strategy) or make sustainable and social proposals (social strategy), unless these aims are achieved through an empowering process that transforms our current values and relations (empowering strategy).”

Key words: Grassroots innovation. Strategic Niche Management. Learning. Energy Transition. Strategies. Som Energia.

1. Introduction

New social innovations to deal with the sustainability challenges society is facing are continuously emerging in different realms. Although the most visible of them are focused on technological proposals and developed by traditional incumbent private sector organisations or public institutions, civil society organisations are also experimenting with innovative practical proposals and playing an important role in the development of sustainable practices. These civil society initiatives have been conceptualised as *grassroots innovations* (GIs) (Seyfang & Smith 2007) and can be defined as "*(n)etworks of activists and organizations generating novel bottom-up solutions for sustainable development*" (Seyfang & Smith, 2007, p.585). They have been studied in relation to a great variety of topics, such as community energy projects, community food networks, community currencies, sustainable housing, local material recycling or community-based water and sanitation (Seyfang, 2009; Smith et al., 2016).

In these debates, some scholars have focused on the transformative dimension of some GIs. They underscore the fact that, in some cases, GIs not only build and explore alternative and more sustainable models in different realms and systems, but also propose more just and democratic models, through innovation processes which are led by people's needs and aspirations (Pellicer-Sifres et al., 2016). In this line, some scholars have recently tried to examine the exact meaning of *transformation* (Fressoli et al., 2014; Pellicer-Sifres et al., 2016; Smith et al., 2016). They have developed research to better characterise transformative grassroots initiatives, addressing how they are mobilising citizens' values (Martin & Upham 2016) and contributing to more just societies (coined, in Smith et al., 2014 as grassroots innovation movements; and in Pellicer-Sifres et al., 2016 as grassroots social innovation for human development). They agree that GIs are transformative when they deliberately and effectively pursue justice as a key aim¹. However, despite the interest and importance of the transformative dimension of GIs, research has essentially focused on the definition and sense of *transformation*. No research has specifically been conducted on how transformative perspectives, strategies and actions emerge.

Most authors have studied grassroots innovations from Strategic Niche Management literature (SNM), in order to understand how niches and initiatives strategise, act, and develop in relation with their aims (for a systematic review, see Hossain, 2016). In this strand of research, a Multi-Level Perspective has proved useful for contextualising SNM and providing a deeper understanding of how the socio-technical proposals of GIs change over time.

The research has also focused on niche-internal processes, in order to understand how learning emerges at the core of the initiative and its contribution to niche development (Schot & Geels, 2008; Geels & Raven, 2006; Seyfang & Haxeltine, 2012; Byrne, 2009). This research has identified that "*most learning will contribute to niche development if it is not only directed*

¹ Note that this is not the case of all initiatives found under the GI label: from literature to sustainability transition, we found cases of GIs that pursue sustainability or the interests of a specific group of people. We base this paper on our previous work and stance on what a transformative GI is (Pellicer-Sifres et al., 2016), and we are especially interested in exploring those grassroots initiatives which, apparently, mobilise people, reframe citizen's values and contribute to just societies. From hereon, we will refer to them as Grassroots Social Movements.

at the accumulation of facts and data, i.e., first-order learning, but also enable changes in cognitive frames and assumptions, i.e., second-order learning” Schot & Geels (2008, p. 541). However, to the author’s knowledge, no specific research has been found on understanding the role of learning in relation to transformative change.

It is reasonable to suppose that this second-order learning is key for transformative developments, for this reason authors such as Mezirow (2000), name it “transformative learning”. However, these questions have not been further explored, either in SNM and MLP literature or in grassroots social movement research—which is quite surprising given the aspirations to bring about transformative development present in these literatures.

The aim of the paper, then, is to address the shortcomings mentioned and explore how transformative change takes place through learning in grassroots innovations. In more specific terms, the aim is to explore which drivers and which (first- and second-order) learning results in grassroots initiatives that are relevant to promoting transformative strategies to sustainability.

To explore these topics, we connect the aforementioned ideas on SNM and MLP with some ideas from critical learning literature. We consider insights from Learning in Social Action (LSA) discussions, as long as they focus on informal and incidental learning in social struggles and political activity (Foley 1999). We complement this with ideas on transformative learning from Mezirow (2000), as they may be relevant for understanding the different levels and the transformative nature of some learning. Through the connection of these discussions with SNM and MLP literature we build a heuristic framework to help us better understand how to characterise the space where learning emerges; what the drivers that motivate its appearance are, and what outcomes emerge.

To address the aim of the paper, we will explore the niche of the citizens’ energy movement in Spain, in particular, the case of the grassroots initiative Som Energia—the first green energy cooperative—which has a remarkable spirit of activism and social mobilisation. This research was conducted during the period of 2014–2016 using a purely qualitative methodology, based on a mixture of techniques including in-depth document analysis, semi-structured interviews, participant observation and participation as active members of the cooperative.

The paper is organised as follows: in Section 2 we provide theoretical basic concepts of LSA, SNM, MLP and grassroots social movements literature, and connect them in order to propose a theoretical framework. Section 3 presents the case study, and section 4 explains the methodology used to gather and analyse the information. In Section 5, we discuss the key findings on the drivers of learning processes (5.1); and we explore the outcomes of learning (5.2) by characterising this learning and connecting it with three different strategies proposed by the grassroots initiative, thus highlighting some reflections on its transformative character. Finally, in section 6, we present some concluding remarks on our study.

2. Theoretical background

Although learning has been highlighted in SNM literature as a relevant aspect in order to understand how alternative framings that confront the current regime are generated (Geels & Raven, 2006; Kemp et al., 1998; Schot & Geels, 2008); only a handful of studies have explored

it and characterised it in depth. To deal with this shortcoming, we use theoretical insights from literature in adult education on the topic on Learning in Social Action in order to characterise where learning emerges, what the drivers are, and what outcomes result.

Learning has been looked at from various disciplines and angles, including cognitive psychology, social psychology, (adult) education studies, management studies, innovation studies, policy science studies, development studies and complex systems thinking (Loeber et al. 2007). Among them, and for the purposes of this article, we choose to discuss learning from one specific literature within the field of adult education, which is the one on the topic on “Learning in Social Action”. It is inspired by authors such as Foley, Holst, Hall, Chaudry, Margaret or Steinklammer, who focus particularly on the processes of *learning in people’s struggles*, through participation in a social movement or NGO, in hegemonic practices, in resistance experiences, that is to say, “through the involvement in social action”. We are especially interested in the incidental learning processes arising from and contributing to engagement in social struggles.

These topics and interests are not exactly those dealt by authors from social learning literature, such as Bandura, Argyris and Schön. For example (Bandura 1997) focused on explaining how individuals learn from society from a cognitive perspective of learning influenced by context and social norms; (Argyris & Schön 1978), from an organisational management perspective, were less focused on individual learning and more on how group learning occurs and how it can be dynamically structured and facilitated.

From our literature review of the many approaches to adult learning, we considered Learning in Social Action to be an inspiring literature on which to develop our theoretical point of view, due to the fact that our research is based on one specific type of GIs: those grassroots social movements that can be considered as social organisations of citizens involved in democratic action for social change. Although, as (Hossain 2016) acknowledges, there is a huge spectrum of experiences with different characteristics, aims, challenges, and achieved outputs, in this paper we focus on those grassroots initiatives that can be considered to be engaged in social action.

LSA literature argues that involvement in social action and struggle itself becomes a form of adult learning—dynamic, incidental and resistance learning—in which people unlearn dominant oppressive discourses and instead learn oppositional, liberatory ones. Foley’s book (1999) makes a vital contribution to theorising and making explicit these incidental learning processes arising from and contributing to engagement in a range of social struggles, recognising its importance, its complexity, its non-neutrality and its unavoidable link with ethical judgements and choices. Based on this definition, adult learning in processes of social action can be described as emergent, informal, non-planned, tacit and incidental, based on dynamic relationships, and embedded in power relations (Belda-Miquel et al., 2016).

Holst (2002) remarks that through a participation in a social movement, people learn numerous skills and ways of thinking analytically and strategically as they struggle to understand their movement in motion. “As coalitions are formed people’s understanding of interconnectedness of relations within a social totality become increasingly sophisticated”. (Hols, 2002, pp. 87–88). This learning takes place through relationships, in permanent and

dynamic processes, embedded in particular contexts, where social, political, economic and cultural factors are at play (Margaret 2010).

2.1. The space: Grassroots Social Movements as key spaces for learning in social action

Grassroots Social Movements are based on civil society forms of organisation that include a broad diversity of social actors, who interact with each other through collaboration, mobilisation, self-organisation and self-recognition, often basing their relationship on new arrangements that differ from formal institutions (horizontal structures, democratic decision-making processes, and spaces to practice deliberative democracy) (Smith et.al, 2014). They can be considered to be political actors since they are contributing to unveiling institutional, political and economic injustices (Smith et al., 2016). They confront the regime conventions by promoting new and varied solutions to local-global problems, promoting critical knowledge (opening spaces for reflections about politics of knowledge, distribution of resources, power relations), and generating spaces to learn abilities and attitudes to configure transformative personal and social relations (Pellicer-Sifres et al. 2017).

Drawing on the literature of Learning in Social Action, these learning procedures are shaped by various processes at different levels, from the processes of interactions between individuals and organisations—the micropolitics—to macro processes and trends of change and conflict—the macropolitics (Foley 1999). In fact, these micro and macro processes are also interlinked, and both are moulded by ideologies, discourses, knowledge creation, meanings, representations, etc.

We will now try to better characterise how these micro and macro processes drive learning, and to connect them with ideas from SNM.

2.2. Drivers: how micropolitics inside grassroots movements influence learning

Foley highlights that the *micropolitics* inside the social movements, considered as the interaction between actors in a local and wider contextual level, are one of the key drivers that influence learning (Foley, 1999). Building on ideas from SNM literature, these interactions can occur on two levels: local niche level and global niche level (Geels & Raven, 2006).

On the one hand, the *local niche level* consists of actors who are directly involved in local projects or initiatives, for example, a grassroots social initiative that is promoting alternative means of energy production and consumption. Micropolitics at the local niche level would refer to questions such as how people participating in a grassroots initiative interact with each other, how they get organised, how they develop their practices or make decisions, or how they deal with power relations. These micropolitics can be considered democratic when they are promoting public deliberation, democracy, engagement and agency.

On the other hand, the *global niche level* refers to an emerging field or community which can be considered as a movement, consisting of other actors broadly seeking the same aim and

sharing the same expectations². Looking at the latter example, in a territory (e.g., a country or city) the global level would refer to all community energy initiatives; NGOs and associations working on energy justice issues; policy advocacy organisations and platforms; small and local renewable business, among others. The articulation of common expectations and visions; the building of social networks and sharing learning processes between actors in the niche are crucial for niche development because they contribute to its legitimisation and provide the necessary resources (people, expertise, money) (Schot & Geels 2008). We consider these three processes to understand niche development from a broad, comprehensive perspective: in our understanding, the building of social networks and the articulation of social expectations are part of the micropolitics shaping learning. Moreover, we refer both to collective learning emerging between actors from a same global niche (the learning usually explored in the literature), and to the individual and collective learning emerging at the core of a grassroots innovation initiative.

2.3. Drivers: how macropolitics (regime/landscape) influence learning

Together with the micropolitical influences on the emergence of learning explained above, Foley (1999) considers the macropolitics, understood as the influence of economic and political changes that create conditions and shape social mobilisation.

Multi-Level Perspective theory (Geels, 2002; Geels, 2011) can offer us conceptual and analytical insights in order to specify how these macropolitics work. It represents a theoretical model that characterises society structured on three levels: landscape (long-term trends as dominant values, economic paradigms, institutional logics); regime (the locus of established practices and associated rules that stabilise existing systems) and niche (protective spaces from which innovations with the potential to transform the regime emerge). When regimes are pressured by landscapes, niches may find opportunities to change regimes, if they are mature enough to influence or substitute the regime. Grassroots initiatives can be considered as niches, whose purposes may be oriented towards social justice and public good.

LSA literature also refers to how macro-level trends (such as ideologies) shape the struggles of grassroots movements and thus transformative learning. Quoting Foley (1999, p.26), *“unlearning of dominant, oppressive ideologies and discourses and the learning of oppositional, liberatory ones are central to processes of emancipatory action”*. In short, these political, economic and cultural factors (Margaret 2010), considered as drivers, and the interactions among multiple niches and regimes and landscape shape this learning.

2.4. Outcomes: the kind of learning that emerges and its influence on shaping strategies

Learning that may emerge from social action can adopt different forms, depending on its connection with technical, political, cultural, social or relationship issues, among others. Mezirow (2000) classifies two main levels of learning: 1) first-order or instrumental and more

² The “global” level does not have to mean on a worldwide level, it can be at the city level, or in the specific territory where the local niche is involved.

pragmatic learning (how to do something, changes in some routine or habit); 2) second-order, considered as transformative learning (changes in mental frames and assumptions).

Regarding first-order learning, experience leads to a reflection that may allow a new action or plan. Second-order learning represents a deeper level of reflection, it appears when the current paradigm is questioned, when people become aware and when a new understanding of reality occurs, which can be tested through a new experience (which implies going back to a first-order learning). That is to say: learning is transformative when we "*transform our frameworks through a critical reflection of the assumptions about our beliefs, interpretations, mindsets and viewpoints*" (Mezirow, 2000, p.35).

In our study, we aim to unveil the transformative learning at the core of grassroots social movements and explore how the macropolitics and micropolitics are actually drivers that promote it. At the same time, we consider that these learnings emerge with the aspiration to influence, in turn, changes in both macropolitical and micropolitical dynamics. The form and scope of these potential influences can be understood by exploring the strategies proposed by the grassroots innovation initiatives in order to pursue their aims and transform the socio-technical system. By "strategies" we refer to "the way to achieve the desirable change", in other words, which actions, activities, programmes and outcomes we are planning to promote those changes on socio-technical systems that the initiative pursues.

The literature does not further characterise what "transformative strategies" actually means. Recently, authors such as Schot & Kanger (2016) connect it with the notion of "deep transition", which is considered as a "*series of connected individual transitions in a wide range of socio-technical systems, (...) that involves changing a set of deeply embedded meta-rules shared among several socio-technical systems*". Authors like Schot & Steinmueller (2016) propose that transformative change has to be understood as a "*process to address a wide range of societal challenges including inequality, unemployment and climate change*". It should allow, then, for "*deep learning, challenges to dominant views, and nurturing a greater diversity of options*". From our point of view, a "transformative strategy" is that strategy which is transformative in both: in its ends (outcomes as changes in socio-technical systems) and in its means (processes that contribute to transformative learning). However, since this is a current and open debate, it is our contention that revealing the nature of the transformative learning emerging from grassroots social movements, and the strategies inspired by this learning, can offer some insight into what a transformative strategy is.

2.5. Connecting concepts: analytical framework

In Figure 1, we provide a heuristic framework, coming from the combination of the ideas indicated above, based on the three categories: spaces, drivers and outcomes. It aims to provide an analytical tool in order to explore learning emerging from grassroots innovation initiatives, its influences and its implications in terms of the strategic action of niches.

Figure 1: Framework proposed to explore learning in Grassroots Social Movements

Figure 2: Interactions and influences for the emergence of learning, in niche dynamics. (Adapted from Geels and Raven, 2006)

Figure 2 presents a dynamic view of the interactions between the elements from our framework. It is based on Geels and Raven (2006), where the focus of the analysis is at niche level (not on regime and landscape, which explains why they appear mixed).

3. Case study: energy struggle in Spain and the case of Som Energia as a grassroots social movement

In this section, we present a summary of the case study. In other words, following the nomenclature used on the framework proposed, we hereupon describe “the space” for learning in social action.

The Spanish electricity market is characterised by considering electricity as a commodity, and consequently, the supply is cut off when energy bills are not paid, without considering specific social situations and family composition. Technology relies on big plants, mostly dependent on fossil fuels, and controlled by a few companies. Regulations are complex and based on techno-scientific knowledge, so it is difficult for users to properly understand the energy market and make decisions to choose the best energy offer (Latonda, 2013). Moreover, 95% of Spain’s electricity, 99.7% of the distribution and 79.5% of the commercialisation is generated by just five companies (APPA, 2013), meaning that the Spanish energy sector is an oligopoly (Barcia & Romero, 2014). Currently, politics and regulations are being criticised, since they hinder the development of new renewable energies and self-consumption installations. They also contribute to Spain having the second-highest electricity prices in Europe and are not tackling an increasing rise in fuel poverty (Tirado et al., 2014; Urkidi et al., 2015).

This regime combined with a broader context embedded in an economic crisis and an awakening of activism in civil society (Lillo & Pellicer-Sifres, 2014) have made the emergence of a variety of energy-related initiatives possible, such as citizens' cooperatives, policy advocacy associations, social enterprises, projects dedicated to retrofitting energy efficiency measures or other means. Among them, Som Energia arose in 2010 as the first renewable energy cooperative to operate in both parts of the cycle: in the production, developing new small-scale renewable energy projects; and in the commercialisation, supplying electricity from renewable sources.

The cooperative has experienced an unexpected growth, increasing from 300 members when it was founded in 2010, to more than 38,000 members in 2016. It is considered in Spain as a pioneer, having explored and implemented a new organisational structure to provide energy, hitherto unknown (Riutort 2015). Since its formation, what are known as “local groups” have flourished across all of Spain, consisting of groups of highly-motivated activists and politically conscious people, all of them volunteers, who organise conferences, debates and regular meetings across the country. In these meetings, they defend and explain how to promote a new culture of energy consumption based on responsibility and democracy, on renewable energies, energy efficiency and savings. Currently, 65 local groups exist, although they are unevenly distributed around Spain, depending on the region.

These groups have emerged from the bottom-up, they do not have a set agenda and all of them function with a horizontal decision-making structure. Each group has its own regular meetings, and they all meet together at different times during the year, for training or for strategic planning purposes. Apart from these physical encounters, there are also digital platforms and they use digital tools to stay in touch, share, discuss and debate throughout the year.

Broadly speaking, activists define the strategy and run the cooperative, discussing and taking positions in the many spaces and means of participation. The board of the cooperative is composed of activists, and takes its final decisions based on these democratic discussions from the grassroots.

4. Methodology

Following the classification of ontological and epistemological paradigms (Lincoln et al., 2011), our assumptions were based on both interpretative paradigms (since we consider knowledge to be mediated by the positions of people in social systems) and critical paradigms (knowledge is, at the same time, mediated by the positions of people in social systems). Our methodological approach is qualitative, based on a case study, and it combines a theory-driven approach (elements from our theoretical framework guide the first round of analysis) together with an empirically based approach in a second round of analysis and in the discussion and conclusions stages.

The case study is the renewable energy cooperative Som Energia, a citizenship cooperative that produces and commercialises renewable energy. The special feature of this case study which is relevant for our research is the existence of “local groups” all over Spain. These are

groups of highly motivated activists and politically conscious people. In our research, we have explored learning emerging among participants of these groups.

During the research, several methods were used to gather the information: semi-structured interviews, participant observation and documental analysis (Corbetta 2007).

A total of nine semi-structured interviews were made with key actors from six local groups. The sample was intentionally and strategically selected. We sought, on one hand, to guarantee comparability between groups with a certain level of maturity and durability (existing from the beginning, being active and popular in their territory). On the other hand, we aimed to guarantee variability, comparing people from the groups doing different activities and occupying different roles. Accessibility was another factor that influenced the sample. Consequently, four different people interviewed belonged to the group that the authors had easiest access to. Table 1 summarises the main characteristics of the sample.

Participant observation was carried out between 2014 and 2016. The aim was to understand the micropolitics internal to the organisation (processes, dynamics, relations, roles, networking, strategies, tensions, relevant debates, among others). During the three years of research, two of the authors assisted regular meetings from local group 1 (29 meetings), to 3 annual assemblies, to 3 annual “strategic planning meetings”³ and to 3 annual “training meetings”⁴. Furthermore, the authors participated in two other social initiatives concerning energy mobilisation (a local NGO⁵ and a national platform⁶, both working for the transformation of the energy model through policy advocacy activities). This allowed us to further understand the macropolitics (landscape and regime) of the Spanish energy model. The notes from all these meetings were firstly taken as condensed notes, and afterwards expanded and differentiated between objective facts and the authors’ interpretations.

Documental analysis complemented this primary information. The secondary sources reviewed were generally produced by Som Energia (the minutes of fifteen annual meetings that have taken place since 2012, debates on a digital platform for sharing and discussing relevant topics; and reports from a six-month participatory strategic planning process carried out between September and January 2016) and, in particular, by those local groups from our sample (blog posts). News, websites and public statements were also considered so as to expand the understanding of the Spanish energy regime.

Qualitative analysis software (Atlas.ti) was used to carry out a thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke 2006) on interview transcriptions, observatory participant notes and secondary sources. At the beginning, four deductive codes (Miles et al., 2014) were defined based on the categories from our theoretical framework: micropolitics (subcodes: local niche and global niche), macropolitics, learning (subcodes: first and second) and strategies. During the analysis, six inductive codes (Miles et al., 2014) emerged as descriptive information, related with topics

³At this annual meeting, around 40–60 people, the main activists from all over Spain, join together over one weekend. In this space, the strategic planning of the cooperative (strategy in the mid-long term) is discussed.

⁴At this annual meeting, around 250–300 people, involves members from the entire cooperative, even if they are not involved in any local group. This is a training space, where there are conferences and workshops on relevant and current topics about the energy model.

⁵Ingeniería Sin Fronteras – Valencia. <https://www.isf.es/>

⁶Plataforma por un Nuevo Modelo Energético - <http://www.nuevomodeloenergetico.org/>

about sustainability, about social justice and about social relations, and related to strategies with commercial, with social and with empowering aims.

Once codified, the data compilation was visualised by two matrices (which Table 2 and Table 3 are based on, respectively). The analysis of both matrices found repeated patterns (Braun & Clarke 2006) that allowed us to establish the connections between learnings and strategies. Finally, the interpretation of these results according to our theoretical framework was presented as a diagram (represented by Figure 3, which is included at the end of section 4).

It is important to mention that two of the authors have been participating as activists in the initiative since 2012, both in the activist space (participating in a local group) and in the political space (being member of the board council). This means that when we adopted the role of researchers and academics, we already had knowledge of the possibilities and challenges of the organisation, and also strong personal relationships with activists and staff. Bearing in mind the role of the “insider” that carries out “real world research” (Robson 1993), we were aware of the risks and assumed that this could bring both opportunities—for example, access to data; as well as constraints—for example, previous knowledge and assumptions may influence the analysis of findings. Having this bias in mind, we sought to guarantee the validity of the data and verify our findings by several triangulation methods: between techniques (finding patterns that repeatedly appeared in the three instruments used); between sources (we shared and discussed findings with other activists with similar profiles as those from our sample) and between researchers (data analysis was performed by two of the authors of this paper, but only one of them was an activist/insider-outsider). Finally, we also asked for feedback from the nine people interviewed and discussed our findings in a group 1 meeting.

Group	Gender	Age	Years involved in Som Energia	Main tasks developed	Activist Background
E1	M	35	5	Administrative. Dissemination	Yes
E2	M	38	2	Public talks. Renewable energy projects studies	No
E3	F	48	5	Dissemination	Yes
E4	F	50	5	Dissemination. Energy efficiency training courses	No
E5	M	26	3	Public talks. Debates. Policy advocacy	Yes
E6	M	30	6	Coordinator of the group. Public talks. Debates. Collaboration with public administration	Yes
E7	F	35	4	Public talks. Conferences at university. Energy efficiency advice to SMEs ⁷	No
E8	F	32	4	Coordinator of the group. Public talks. Energy efficiency advice to local business	No
E9	M	35	5	Coordinator of the group. Public talks oriented to public administration and to neighbourhood communities	No

Table 1: **Key features of the sample**

⁷ SME means Small and Medium Enterprises

5. Analysis and discussion

In this section we present and discuss the case study (“the space” described on section 3), basing our discussion on the elements proposed in the theoretical section (“drivers” and “outcomes”).

5.1. Drivers of learning

5.1.1. How micropolitics shape the emergence of learning

To examine the drivers of learning, we will first address how micropolitics—the individual interactions within Som Energia and the interactions of Som Energia with other initiatives in the niche—shape the learning emerging in those participating in the cooperative:

Each group has its own meetings and is autonomous. It sets its own agenda, depending on the interests of the people involved, and the opportunities offered in their local context. Some groups are more involved in commercial activities to increase the number of members of the cooperative (fairs concerning the social and solidarity economy or ecological issues; talks in neighbourhood associations or in schools); others develop projects in their own local territories (engaging and promoting local commerce; initiatives against fuel poverty); others are more focused on policy advocacy activities (demonstrations, reports to inform policies, etc.). Through the development of these activities, all those interviewed expressed that they have discovered the social perspective and consequence of energy, shifting from technical interests (like engineering projects) to social and political issues (fuel poverty, energy sovereignty, etc.). Furthermore, regarding first-order learning, they remarked how much they have learnt in relation to capabilities such as communication, working in groups, creating influence, or acquiring a good level of IT skills and social network management.

These initiatives are rarely carried out by an isolated actor but in connection with other local actors, such as other initiatives in the social and solidarity economy or other ecological or political organisations. This fact makes them feel they belong to a broader movement, which, as one interviewee stated *“is already bringing change to society”* (E1). This enhances people’s agency and their positive attitude to promote change. One of the most valued learnings was the discovery of these other social initiatives, most of them in their own territories, where best practices enable them to live in greater alignment with their principles. In five cases with interviewees, we found that what had started as first-order learning (knowing the existence of other ways to consume food, telecommunications, clothes, invest money, etc.) had evolved into second-order learning through a deeper reflection, the questioning of the power of consumption as a tool for social change and the transformation of power relations.

“I have realised that people have the capacity to change things. But we only become aware when we see that our actions have consequences. (...) I have realised that we can create a lot of pressure through our decisions about consumption. Consumption is a powerful tool for social change”. (E.6)

Each group (composed of between 5–20 people) has its own regular meetings (weekly to monthly) which are based on horizontal procedures. Moreover, three annual encounters have been created where people from all groups (those who are most active and involved—around

250 people) join together to discuss relevant topics, self-train, and to think about the cooperative's strategic planning for the following years. Five of the interviewees had not previously participated in social organisations based on horizontal procedures. For them, assemblies, meetings, discussions, and the fact that decisions were taken collectively and not by official managers, provided relevant spaces for learning instrumental skills, such as the capacity to deliberate, express their own voice, respect other points of view and learn from conflict.

This first-order learning has important implications, in some cases for developing second-order reflections on how the way as we relate to each other can also be a powerful element to promote social change in our society. For some, practising self-management, participating in decision-making processes based on consensus and not on hierarchical decisions, considering all voices, and recognising the diversity of perspectives and forms of knowledge, makes them rethink society through the lenses of those power relations that we need to change, and through the lenses of agency and people's capacity to promote that change. In other words, they try to construct their organisation based on the same values that would wish to find in the society they would like to live in. The following quote illustrates this reflection:

“And then you realise that this is not about energy... it is about what our role in society is. (...) Who has the power? Who takes decisions? Who is excluded? It is not about one energy source or another. It is about who decides that. If we want to change this, we first have to change how we relate to each other, and how we defend our ideas or not”. (E2)

5.1.2. How macropolitics shape the emergence of learning?

We will now address how macropolitics—the multilevel interaction between landscape, regime and niches—shape the learning acquired in the participants of Som Energia:

Up until the winter of 2012, fuel poverty was a hidden and nameless problem in Spanish society (Pellicer-Sifres & Lillo, 2014). It was the pressure of civil society and different social organisations who, aligned with the mass media and using social networks, managed to make the existence of fuel poverty visible as an emerging but critical problem today, the responsibility for which was attributed both to government and the energy oligopoly. Som Energia took part in these first mobilisations and its members from different local groups were engaged in various activities, such as: workshops with social workers, proposing projects for local authorities, diffusion talks or training about how to decrease energy bills.

The Som Energia members involved in these initiatives explained that they learnt a lot about fuel poverty regulations and procedures (first-order learning). This transformed into deeper (second-order) learning when activists became aware of the power relations between politics and the oligopoly embedded in the non-transparent methods employed to determine electricity prices as well as the inefficiency and unjust nature of social benefits.

“We suddenly started to be asked to give some talks in charities and in other institutions that are helping people to pay their bills. And we wanted to do it, but we realised we also were ignorant about all these things. The system makes us ignorant. Even me, with a technical background and with ecological awareness, I had no idea about how to understand my energy bill, I didn't know whether I was paying more than I should”. (E.7)

With reference to policies, from 2004 to 2008 there was a period in Spain known as the renewable energy boom (Gómez et al., 2016), when there was a huge uptake of renewable energies built on massive financial investment in renewable energies promoted by the government. However, from 2008 onwards, this period was tainted by rampant debt in the power sector, leading to the act of Parliament that put an end to feed-in tariffs in 2010, with retroactive force. This measure caused the bankruptcy of renewable energy investors, as well as the beginning of a period of legal uncertainty that made the development of new renewable installations impossible.

Som Energia's long term aim to produce enough electricity to meet the demands of its members was suddenly interrupted, and this opened a wide debate in the cooperative about the next steps, and which kind of projects to support. Various debate spaces were prepared, as well as talks with experts on legislation and on engineering design projects, in order to make these decisions by considering all the risks.

During this process, participants explained that they have mainly learnt about legislation and technical issues related to designing renewable energy projects and self-consumption. E.2 and E.4 comment that the discussion on the criteria used to decide which projects to support has also been useful to understand and discuss what is meant when they say they propose a "decentralised" model: small projects that are sustainable, owned in a participatory way, connected with local actors and institutions. Furthermore, discovering the alternatives proposed have led to them to reflect more deeply (second-order) on the social and solidarity economy, and about the power of collective creativity.

Several factors influenced the evolution of Som Energia, among which we remark the context of economic, political and social crisis, the opacity of the energy model burdened by cases of corruption, and a widespread feeling of indignation against the power of the oligopoly and the revolving doors⁸ between energy companies and the Government⁹. This has to be understood as being embedded in a wider setting of corruption, loss of credibility in the political class and the emergence of an active civil society during the period of intense social mobilisation of the 15-M *movement*¹⁰.

Moreover, getting inside the complex architecture of the energy model, discovering its opacity and understanding the power of the oligopoly, in the nine cases led to people developing a more critical view and thinking about power system relations and about the power of knowledge, as the following quote suggests:

"They don't just control energy, but they also control the production of knowledge, information channels, etc. The struggle is not just material; it is also epistemological".
(E.6)

⁸ "Revolving doors" is understood as the phenomenon whereby senior politicians are hired by energy companies immediately upon their retirement from politics.

⁹The newspaper, El Mundo, reported in February 2014 that forty-three senior politicians were hired by energy companies after leaving politics (Suárez 2014).

¹⁰The 15M was the Spanish antecedent of the Occupy movement, which exploded after 15th May 2011, and involved the occupation of public spaces and huge mobilisations of people.

5.2. Outcomes of learning

5.2.1. Identifying the content of learning: sustainability, social justice and social relations

Table 2 summarises the different types of learning identified in the two previous sections, that is: the first- and second-order learning that emerged in the core of the cooperative's members, due to the influence of macro- or micropolitical issues. Departing from the learning mentioned, we can identify that it took place in relation to three different but interlinked issues: sustainability and market operation; social justice; and social relations. For each of these issues, first- and second-level learning emerged.

FIRST ORDER - INSTRUMENTAL (Learning about...)
<p>About sustainability (renewable energies and efficiency) and about the energy market operation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - About the development of new renewable energy projects: technology, legislation, regulations, calculation, inversion, profitability - About energy efficiency measures and savings - About the electricity market: operation, price-fixing system, legislation, regulation <p>About social justice issues:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - About the social implications of energy: fuel poverty, inequity, global implications, power centralised in big infrastructures owned by a few companies - About measures to combat fuel poverty: procedures to change contracts with companies, regulation, understanding energy bills, social actors involved - About the social and solidarity economy: about discovering new grassroots initiatives, promoting alternative ways of production and consumption <p>About social relations: about communication and relation skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - About skills to communicate with and influence others - About IT and digital social networks skills - About skills such as capacity to deliberate, express their own voice, respect and learn from conflict

(These arrows mean that both orders are interconnected. One contributes to the emergence of the other and vice versa)

SECOND ORDER - CRITICAL (Learning about...)
<p>About sustainability urgency and about energy market power relations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - About energy linked with climate change crisis. Local-global connections - About power relations between politics and the oligopoly; non-transparent and unjust methods to fix electricity prices; inefficiency and inequity of social benefits - About different ways of exercising power: generating complex, non-transparent and inaccessible knowledge; imposing neoliberal schools of thought <p>About social justice issues:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - About fuel poverty issues: a deeper understanding of considering energy as a right; critical self-reflection on own habits and thoughts - About current model values, not aligned with equity, diversity, sustainability <p>About social relations: about the way we organise. About people's capacity to promote change (agency)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - About the way we can be organised/associated in society, based on values such as solidarity, recognition, equity, trust, friendship. - About the way we relate to each other, as a powerful element to promote social change - About people's capacity to imagine and develop, from the collective, new models of business in renewable production and investment - About the potential of consumption as a tool for social change - About people's capacity to join with other actors and create a movement with a broader influence

Table 2: First- and second-order learning emerging among people participating in Som Energia

5.2.2. Identifying transition strategies emerging from learning on sustainability, social justice and social relations

Although all members of the cooperative and the other actors from the global niche level might be expected to share a common aim—to change the energy model to one that is more sustainable, distributed, democratic and equitable—there is no common agreement about the best strategy to achieve this end. From our three years of participant observation, and from the analysis of minutes, debates and reports, we identified that, although without being formulated in an explicit way, three main strategies were being proposed in Som Energia (Som Energia, 2016). Through the in-depth interviews, we found connections on how the various kinds of learning listed in Table 2 influence the various strategies proposed or supported by our interviewees.

Note that we have identified three types of strategies, named “commercial”, “social”, and “empowering”. Each type of strategy is connected with one of the types of learning identified before: learning on sustainability and energy market leads to a commercial strategy; learning on social justice leads to a social strategy and learning on social relations leads to an empowering strategy.

From the beginning, the cooperative was created as an alternative to the oligopoly system, with the aim of decarbonising the energy mix by developing as many renewable energy projects as the cooperative’s members demanded. It had thus implicitly implied a “commercial strategy” in order to increase the number of customers and take power back from the oligopoly. In fact, this still remains in the mainstream strategy present in most discourse from the cooperative’s members, such as *“We need to include more and more clients”*(repeated idea found during participant observation).

Our analysis found that people who support this “commercial strategy” were those members who remarked that their main learning acquired after being involved in Som Energia was that related to the urgency for sustainability and on energy market power relations. Statements such as *“Climate change is here and we are still using fossil fuels... it is urgent to change”* (E.3) or *“It’s true that we are starting to change things in the electric sector, but we are still nobody, there are currently only thirty thousand of us, which is nothing in comparison with the big five”* (E.9) suggest that these people were principally concerned by issues of renewable energy, climate change and oligopoly power. This learning was rendered in the proposal of actions such as commercial campaigns or developing new business models to finance and build new renewable energy projects. Drivers coming from macropolitical issues, such as the pressure coming from the evidence of climate change or citizens’ indignation at the revolving-doors between politics and oligopoly board members are especially influential in the emergence of this learning.

However, our study found that two other strategy proposals have emerged among activists from the local group: for people whose main critical learning was about social justice issues, although the renewable issue was important, it was not a central element. They proposed something that on our analysis we have targeted as “social strategy”, mainly focused on promoting an equitable access to energy, complaints against fuel poverty, revolving doors, unfair laws that impede self-consumption and the expectation to achieve energy sovereignty poverty. The following statements provide evidence of this attitude:

“As an energy actor, we have to work to achieve the goal that there’s not a single person that does not have access to energy”(E.7); “We have to recover our sovereignty, and be able to produce our own energy”. (E.8)

Interviewers suggest developing lobby and policy advocacy activities to influence social and energy policies, combat fuel poverty, and develop self-production business models in order to promote local renewable projects. Macropolitical features such as the Spanish crisis context, citizens’ indignation and the regime’s discourses and policies were key drivers to influence people’s awareness and learning about social inequity. Furthermore, the lack of support and legal uncertainty involved in developing new renewable energy plants, together with micropolitical interaction with other actors from the social and solidarity economy, impelled activists to react and seek renewable projects in order to achieve people’s energy sovereignty.

Finally, the third strategy, coined as “empowering”, was proposed by those people who have more internalised learning related to social relations, that is to say, to the way we organise and to people’s capacity to promote change (agency), as this quote suggests:

“We need to develop actions so as to make people aware of their power to change the system. To fight against the current energy model is just the excuse for that”. (E.5)

The core aims of this strategy are to promote new models in the way we relate to each other, based on horizontal relations, with respect to diversity, in order to promote an active and critical citizenship, enhancing their agency. Within this strategy, it is fundamental to promote horizontal and democratic structure and processes, and to create spaces, methodologies and tools to exercise participation and deliberative democracy; while the growth of the cooperative is not relevant in terms of the number of members. The greater the intensity of the drivers from interactions on the local niche level (such as self-management and horizontal procedures), along with connections with other emerging bottom-up initiatives in other sectors based on the same principles, the more likely it is that this kind of learning emerges.

As our theoretical framework noted, the influences of the interconnections and drivers are mutual, complex and bidirectional: on the one hand, macropolitical and micropolitical drivers influence the emergence of learning and, consequently, of the proposal of different strategies. At the same time, the development of these strategies explicitly aims to influence micro- and macropolitical issues, as summarised in Table 3 and Figure 3.

Table 3 and Figure 3 contain the same information, but Table 3 presents it with more detail and explanation while Figure 3 presents it in relation with our theoretical framework (see Figure 1).

Table 3: Learning, strategies and influences on micro- and macropolitics

Figure 3: Learning drivers and outcomes for the case of Som Energia

Hence, findings suggest that learning is an element of influence in the strategies formulated at niche level to achieve sustainability. Taking into account the broad ideas about transformative strategies presented in our theoretical framework, from our case study we could suggest that strategies towards sustainability are transformative since, apart from scaling up (“commercial” strategy) and attending to social and sustainability problems (“social” strategy), they are achieved through an “empowering” process. That is to say: the strategy promotes a radical change to the current paradigm and enhanced agency so people can bring change to society (which, in some way, represents the core value of an “empowering” strategy). Our results suggest that this can be done through enhancing people’s agency; opening up opportunities to exercise participation and deliberation that may foster critical views and practices; permitting the emergence of learning that enables the appearance of a series of attributes—knowledge, values, attitudes, skills—that question the current paradigm and drive people to actively change it.

6. Concluding remarks

The aim of the paper was to explore what kind of learning is emerging at the core of grassroots innovation movements, in order to propose a characterisation to better understand to what extent and how this learning is contributing to transformative sustainability changes in society.

To address this aim, we firstly proposed a framework built on LSA literature, using ideas from SNM and MLP literature. We explore the influence of micropolitical and macropolitical aspects as drivers for the emergence of first and second order learning. In our framework, we propose that learning contributes to influence, in turn, macropolitical and micropolitical dynamics, through promoting different strategies towards sustainability.

We based our analysis on the case of Som Energia, a renewable energy cooperative with a remarkable spirit of activism and social mobilisation. Our framework has been useful in order to explore how external factors (regime and landscape influences) and internal factors (interactions within the niche level) have driven the emergence of first-order learning, such as new knowledge about energy (market, regulations, procedures); about the social and solidarity economy (cooperative culture, new initiatives in other fields); and about new skills on communication and relation to getting engaged in community projects. Moreover, second-order learning emerged, questioning established values and reconsidering issues such as sustainability, power, justice and personal social relations.

Our findings allow us to conclude that the various learnings acquired contribute to propose strategies to sustainability based on different core values. These findings are useful to illustrate that, as discussed earlier, in order to develop radical transformative changes towards sustainability, both, ends and means, matter: it is not enough to merely scale-up the niche or make sustainable and social proposals (outcomes to change the socio-technical system, the ends), unless these aims are achieved through an empowering process that transforms our current values and relations (transformative processes, the means). To this end, we underline the importance of those initiatives that open up spaces that enhance people's agency; foster critical views and practices, connect other initiatives with shared values and restructure power relations.

It is also important to note some reflections about the strengths and limitations of the proposed framework. On the one hand, it allowed us to appreciate the overall connections between context (macropolitics), the internal dynamics of the organisation (micropolitics) and learning, in both sense of interactions. That is to say, the proposed framework is strong on offering insights on: i) the drivers of learning, and ii) the connections drivers and outcomes (i.e., how emerging learning influences micropolitics). This particular strength is due to having used Learning in Social Action literature as theoretical inspiration. This area particularly emphasises the connections between broad political and economic contexts, with internal micropolitics within a social struggles space. The theoretical lenses used have allowed us to find, for example, the "empowering" strategy, since it has forced us to explore connections between context pressures and alternative models of social relations which are already being experimented with.

However, the framework fails to capture the full complexity of the origin of these learnings, since its scope is restricted to the grassroots initiative and it does not offer elements to understand issues related with the personal sphere (for example, politicised background, intelligence, attitude, openness or shyness, among others). Furthermore, our framework limited the classification of learning to 1st and 2nd categories. This is useful to illustrate the richness, variety and complexity of learnings, but it does not allow us to offer pre-defined descriptive or analytical categories, or to make the difference between individual versus

collective learning. Future work can further develop this framework, combining and complemented our ideas on informal learning in social action with ideas from broader Social Learning literature, such as, for example: Bandura, 1997 (who, rooted in the behaviourist paradigm, provides a more comprehensive explanation on individual learning); Argyris and Schön, 1978 (who offer relevant elements for understanding learning in organisational contexts, such as the models of single and double loop learning); Wals, 2007 (who expands the discussion on learning about sustainability) or Reed et. al, 2006 (who deal with learning about sustainability in local communities), among others.

To sum up, this is an exploratory work that aims to broaden the debate on learning in grassroots social movements. From lessons obtained from an empirical case study, explored through the lenses of a conceptual framework based on theoretical elements, this paper stimulates the debate and offers some elements which may be relevant for understanding how micro- and macropolitics model learning in grassroots movements, and how this learning can inspire, in some cases, radical strategies towards sustainability.

7. References

- APPA., 2013. *Estudio del impacto macroeconómico de las energías renovables en España 2013*, Available at: http://www.appa.es/descargas/Informe_2013_Web.pdf.
- Argyris, C. & Schön, D., 1978. *Organizational learning: a theory of action perspective*, Addison-Wesley: Reading, MA.
- Bandura, A., 1997. *Social Learning Theory*, New Jersey: Englewood Cliffs, Prentice Hall.
- Barcia, J. & Romero, C., 2014. *Alta tensión: Por un nuevo modelo energético sostenible, democrático y ciudadano*, Madrid: Icaria.
- Belda-Miquel, S., Boni, A. & Sañudo, M.F., 2016. Informal learning for citizenship building in shared struggles for rights: cases of political solidarity between colombian and spanish organisations. *Voluntas*, 27, pp.249–272.
- Braun, V. & Clarke, V., 2006. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*.
- Byrne, R.P., 2009. *Learning drivers: rural electrification regime building in Kenya and Tanzania*. PhD dissertation. University of Sussex. Available at: <http://sro.sussex.ac.uk/6963/>.
- Corbetta, P., 2007. *Metodología y técnicas de investigación social*, Madrid: McGraw-Hil.
- Foley, G., 1999. *Learning in social action. A contribution to understanding informal education. Global Perspectives on Adult Education and Training*, New York: St. Martin's Press.
- Fressoli, M. et al., 2014. When grassroots innovation movements encounter mainstream institutions: implications for models of inclusive innovation. *Innovation and Development*, 4(2), pp.277–292.
- Geels, F. & Raven, R., 2006. Non-linearity and expectations in niche-development trajectories: Ups and downs in Dutch biogas development (1973-2003). *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 18(3–4), pp.375–392.

- Geels, F.W., 2002. Technological transitions as evolutionary reconfiguration processes: a multi-level perspective and a case-study. *Research Policy*, 31, pp.1257–1274.
- Geels, F.W., 2011. The multi-level perspective on sustainability transitions: Responses to seven criticisms. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 1(1), pp.24–40.
- Gómez, A., Dopazo, C. & Fueyo, N., 2016. The “cost of not doing” energy planning: The spanish energy bubble. *Energy*, 101, pp.434–446.
- Holst, J.D., 2002. *Social movements, civil society and radical adult education*, Westport: Praeger Pub.
- Hossain, M., 2016. Grassroots innovation: A systematic review of two decades of research. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 137, pp.973–981.
- Kemp, R., Schot, J. & Hoogma, R., 1998. Regime shifts to sustainability through processes of niche formation: The approach of strategic niche management. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 10(2), pp.175–195.
- Latonda, M.A., 2013. *El sistema de intermediación de intereses y los grupos de interés en el sector eléctrico español*. PhD Dissertation. Universitat de València.
- Lillo, P. & Pellicer-Sifres, V., 2014. Analysing the influence of the energy model on fuel poverty and the role of citizenship mobilisation : A case study of the platform for a new energy model in Spain. *Queen’s Political Review*, 2(2), pp.25–45.
- Lincoln, Y.S., Lynham, S.A. & Guba, E.G., 2011. Paradigmatic controversies, contradictions, and emerging confluences, revisited. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincon, eds. *The Sage handbook of qualitative research*. London: SAGE Publications, pp. 97–128.
- Loeber, A. et al., 2007. The practical value of theory: conceptualising learning in the pursuit of a sustainable development. In Wageningen Academic Publishers, ed. *Social Learning Towards a Sustainable World: Principles, Perspectives, and Practices*. The Netherlands, pp. 83–97.
- Margaret, J., 2010. Capacity development processes within a social movement: Pākehā Treaty Workers’ Movement. *IDS Bulletin*, 41(3), pp.68–78.
- Martin, C.J. & Upham, P., 2016. Grassroots social innovation and the mobilisation of values in collaborative consumption: a conceptual model. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 134.
- Mezirow, J., 2000. *Learning as Transformation: Critical Perspectives on a Theory in Progress*, New York: Josse- Bass.
- Miles, M.B., Huberman, M.A. & Saldaña, J., 2014. *Qualitative data analysis: a methods sourcebooks. Chapter 11.*
- Pellicer-Sifres, V. et al., 2016. Grassroots Social Innovation for Human Development: an analysis of alternative food networks in the city of Valencia (Spain). *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, Forthcomin.
- Pellicer-Sifres, V. et al., 2017. Grassroots Social Innovation for Human Development: An Analysis of Alternative Food Networks in the City of Valencia (Spain). *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, 2829(May), pp.1–17. Available at: <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0->

85010689282&doi=10.1080%2F19452829.2016.1270916&partnerID=40&md5=aa1730ea01bcc6531b87d4911d5bdc4d.

- Pellicer-Sifres, V. & Lillo, P., 2014. A broader conceptualisation of fuel poverty : Contributions from the Human Development approach. *Queen's Political Review*, 2(2), pp.46–60.
- Reed, M.S., Fraser, E.D.G. & Dougill, A.J., 2006. An adaptive learning process for developing and applying sustainability indicators with local communities. *Ecological Economics*, 59(4), pp.406–418.
- Riutort, S., 2015. *Reapropiación popular de la energía en los albores de una transición incierta. Una contribución a partir del análisis de caso de Som Energia*. PhD Dissertation. Universitat de Barcelona. Available at: <http://www.tdx.cat/handle/10803/380162>.
- Robson, C., 1993. *Real World Research*, Oxford: Blackwell.
- Schot, J. & Geels, F.W., 2008. Strategic niche management and sustainable innovation journeys: theory, findings, research agenda, and policy. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 20(5), pp.537–554.
- Schot, J. & Kanger, L., 2016. Deep transitions: Emergence , acceleration, stabilization and directionality. *SPRU Working Paper Series*, 2057–6668.
- Schot, J. & Steinmueller, W.E., 2016. Framing innovation policy for transformative change: Innovation Policy 3 .0. *SPRU Working Paper Series*, Forthcomin.
- Seyfang, G., 2009. *The new economics of sustainable consumption: Seeds of change*, Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Seyfang, G. & Haxeltine, A., 2012. Growing grassroots innovations: exploring the role of community-based initiatives in governing sustainable energy transitions. *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy*, 30(3), pp.381–400.
- Seyfang, G. & Smith, A., 2007. Grassroots innovations for sustainable development: Towards a new research and policy agenda. *Environmental Politics*, 16(4), pp.584–603.
- Smith, A., Fressoli, M., et al., 2016. *Grassroots Innovation Movements*, Oxon: Routledge.
- Smith, A., Hargreaves, T., et al., 2016. Making the most of community energies: Three perspectives on grassroots innovation. *Environment and Planning A*, 48(2), pp.407–432.
- Smith, A., Fressoli, M. & Thomas, H., 2014. Grassroots innovation movements: Challenges and contributions. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 63(114), p.124.
- Som Energia., 2016. *Marco Estratégico Som Energia 2017-2020: Conclusiones del proceso de reflexión estratégica y organizativa*, Available at: <http://bit.ly/2yX4xfB>.
- Suárez, G., 2014. 43 políticos “enchufados” en eléctricas. *El Mundo*. Available at: <http://www.elmundo.es/cronica/2014/02/23/530881d922601da2168b456c.html>.
- Tirado, S. et al., 2014. *Pobreza energética en España. Análisis de tendencias*, Madrid: ACA.
- Urkidi, L. et al., 2015. *Transiciones Energéticas: sostenibilidad y democracia energética*, Bilbao: Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea, Argitalpen Zerbitzua.
- Wals, A., 2007. *Social learning towards a sustainable world: Principles, perspectives, and*

praxis., Wageningen Academic Pub.